

Dyes Derived from Substituted Phthalic Acids. Part II. 3,4,5,6-Tetraphenyl- and 3,4,5,6-Tetraphenyl- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydro- phthalic Acids. Effect of Introducing Heavy Phenyl Groups in the Phthalic and Partly Saturated Phthalic Acids

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3,4,5,6-Tetraphenylphthalic anhydride and 3,4,5,6-tetraphenyl $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydrophthalic anhydride have been prepared and condensed with different phenols; the phthaleins obtained have been studied analytically and spectrophotometrically. The results obtained have been compared with phthaleins from phthalic acid.

3,4,5,6-Tetraphenylphthalic anhydride (I) and 3,4,5,6-tetraphenyl- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydrophthalic anhydride (II) were condensed with resorcinol, orcinol, phenol, phloroglucinol, pyrogallol, catechol, quinol, and *o*-cresol to yield the corresponding phthaleins. The resorcinolphthaleins were brominated and acetylated. The compounds thus obtained have been analysed and studied spectrophotometrically. The absorption maxima obtained have been compared with those of phthaleins from phthalic acid.

The phthaleins obtained are of the following types:

Type 1(a) from anhydride (I):

Type 1(b) from anhydride (II):

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III(a) and III(b)	: R ¹ = R ² = R ⁴ = H; R ³ = -OH.
IV(a) and IV(b)	: R ¹ = Me; R ² = R ⁴ = H; R ³ = -OH.
V(a) and V(b)	: R ¹ = R ³ = -OH; R ² = R ⁴ = H.
VI(a) and VI(b)	: R ¹ = R ² = H; R ³ = R ⁴ = -OH.
VII(a) and VII(b)	: R ¹ = R ² = R ³ = H; R ⁴ = -OH.
VIII(a) and VIII(b)	: R ¹ = R ³ = R ⁴ = H; R ² = -OH.
IX(a) and IX(b)	: R ¹ = H; R ² = R ⁴ = -Br; R ³ = -OH.
X(a) and X(b)	: R ¹ = R ² = R ⁴ = H; R ³ = -OCOMe.

Type 2(a) from anhydride (I):

XI(a) and XI(b)	: R ¹ = -OH; R ² = H.
XII(a) and XII(b)	: R ¹ = -OH; R ² = -Me.

Type 2(b) from anhydride(II):

A comparative study of the absorption maxima of the dyestuffs shows that the changes in the lower portion of the phthalein dyes (introduction of heavy phenyl groups in the phthalic acid and partly saturated phthalic acid) do not appreciably affect the light absorption. The introduction of heavy phenyl groups in the phthalic acid portion of phthaleins simply increases the intensity of colour.

The slight variations observed in the value of absorption maximum wave length in some cases cannot be properly accounted for unless correct correlation between electronic oscillations and atomic vibrations is established.

EXPERIMENTAL

3,4,5,6-Tetraphenylphthalic anhydride (I) and 3,4,5,6-tetraphenyl- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydrophthalic anhydride (II) were prepared starting from dibenzylketone, benzil, and maleic anhydride¹. The crystallised anhydrides (I) and (II) melted at 290° and 245° respectively. The phthaleins of the type 1(a and b) were obtained as follows:

The anhydrides (I and II) were condensed with different phenols at different temperatures using H₂SO₄ (conc.) as the condensing agent (Table I). The crude phthaleins

1. "Organic Syntheses", Vol. 23, pp. 92-94.

TABLE I

Phthalicins.	Conditions for condensation.		M.P. Appearance.	Colour in		Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		
	Anhydride.	Phenol. Conc. (in drops) & duration.		(Crystalline).	EtOH soln. + alkali.		Found.	Reql. found.		Repl.	
III(a) Resorcinol-TPPh*	I(3g.)	Resorcinol (1.9g.)	4 160-200°; 4 hrs.	265° Dark red	Orange-green; fluorescence	Purple-green; fluorescence	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅	82.6	83.02	4.6	4.40
III(b) Resorcinol-TPDPh*	II(3g.)	Resorcinol (1.9g.)	3 100-80°; 3 hrs.	255° "	Wine-red	Purple-green	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅	82.4	82.75	4.8	4.70
IV(a) Orcinol-TPPh	I(2g.)	Orcinol (1.4g.)	3 150-70°; 4 hrs.	220° "	"	Deep wine-red with green fluorescence	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₅	82.8	83.13	5.9	4.82
IV(b) Orcinol-TPDPh.	II(2g.)	Orcinol (1.4g.)	3 150-70°; 4 hrs.	246° Brick-red	Orange-red	Red-green	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₅	82.65	82.88	5.3	5.10
V(a) Phloroglucinol-TPPh	I(2g.)	Phloroglucinol (1.4g.)	4 180-200°; 4 hrs.	270° Dark red	Red-brown	Red	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇	78.7	79.04	4.3	4.19
V(b) Phloroglucinol-TPDPh	II(2g.)	Phloroglucinol (1.4g.)	4 180-200°; > 300°; 4 hrs.	" "	" "	" "	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇	78.5	78.80	4.6	4.47
VI(a) Pyrogallol-TPPh	I(2g.)	Pyrogallol (1.4g.)	4 180-200°; 4 hrs.	300° Black	Brown	Red-brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇	78.8	79.04	4.2	4.19
VI(b) Pyrogallol-TPDPh	II(2g.)	"	4 180-80°; 4 hrs.	220° Dark brown	Red-brown	Colour inten. sifted	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇	79.1	78.80	4.6	4.47
VII(a) Catechol-TPPh	I(2g.)	Catechol (1.4g.)	4 180-200°; > 300°; 4 hrs.	300° Black	Brown	Red-brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅	82.8	83.02	4.6	4.40
VII(b) Catechol-TPDPh	II(2g.)	"	4 180-200°; 4 hrs.	265° Dark brown	Reddish brown	Colour inten. sifted	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅	82.6	82.75	4.8	4.70
VIII(a) Quinol-TPPh	I(2g.)	Quinol (1.4 g.)	4 160-80°; 4 hrs.	235° "	Brown	Reddish brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅	83.1	83.02	4.52	4.40
VIII(b) Quinol-TPDPh	II(2g.)	"	4 160-80°; 4 hrs.	255° Brown	"	"	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅	82.7	82.75	4.75	4.70
XI(a) Phenol-TPPh	I(2g.)	Phenol (2g.)	8 115-20°; 24 hrs.	208° Pink-red	Wine-red	Deep red	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄	84.6	84.88	4.9	4.83
XI(b) Phenol-TPDPh	II(2g.)	Phenol (2g.)	8 105-10°; 24 hrs.	130° Darkred	Brown	Pink-red	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄	81.2	81.01	5.2	5.12
XII(a) o-Cresol-TPPh	I(3g.)	o-Cresol (2g.)	8 115-20°; 24 hrs.	200° Pale yellow	Pale yellow	Deep pink	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄	81.8	81.02	5.3	5.23
XII(b) o-Cresol-TPDPh	II(2g.)	o-Cresol (2g.)	8 115-20°; 24 hrs.	266° Yellowish brown	Brown	Purple	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄	81.2	81.68	5.36	5.32

*TPPh - 2,4,5,6-tetraphenylphthaloin.
 †PDPh - 2,4,6-trisphenylphthaloin.

thus obtained were purified as recorded in the previous paper². The crystalline products were dried at 110°.

The phthaleins of the type 2(a and b) were obtained slightly in a different way. The anhydride (I or II) was heated with an excess of the phenol (carbolic acid or *o*-cresol) at temperatures ranging from 105° to 120° in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc.) for longer durations (Table I). The condensed semisolid mass was poured in 50 to 75 ml of water and the excess of phenol removed by steam distillation. The residue was extracted with dilute NaOH and filtered. The crude phthalein was then precipitated by adding dilute HCl to the alkaline filtrate. This was purified by decolorising with animal charcoal (in ethanolic solution) and crystallised from ethanol-water (1:1) mixture. The properties of these phthaleins are recorded in Table I.

The resorcinol compounds (IIIa and IIIb) were brominated, using the method of Baeyer³. The resulting tetrabromo compounds (Table II) were crystallised from ethanol and dried at 110°.

The resorcinol compounds (IIIa and IIIb) were also acetylated, using acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate; the diacetates (Table II) obtained were crystallised from ethanol and dried at 110°.

TABLE II

Phthaleins.	M.P.	Colour of crystals.	Colour in		Formula.	Found.	Required.
			EtOH soln.	EtOH+alkali.			
IX(a) Tetrabromo-resorcinol-TPPh*	255°	Red	Red	Red-green	C ₄₄ H ₂₄ O ₅ Br ₄	Br: 33.5%	33.59%
IX(b) Tetrabromo-resorcinol-TPDPh†	225°	Dark red	Do	Do	C ₄₄ H ₂₆ O ₅ Br ₄	Br: 33.3	33.52
X(a) Resorcinol-TPPh diacetate	272°	Dark brown	Brown	Brown	C ₄₈ H ₃₂ O ₇	C: 79.8 H: 4.6	C, 80.0 H, 4.44
X(b) Resorcinol-TPDPh diacetate	283°	Do	Do	Do	C ₄₈ H ₃₄ O ₇	C: 79.6 H: 4.8	C, 79.77 H, 4.7

*TPPh: 3,4,5,6-tetraphenylphthalein.

†TPDPh: 3,4,5,6-tetraphenyl-Δ^{3,5}-dihydrophthalein.

The absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of only a few phthaleins were determined using the British "Unicam" spectrophotometer. The maxima were obtained in neutral and alkaline ethanolic solutions (Tables III and IV). The λ_{max} of phthaleins from phthalic acid were also determined using the same apparatus, under similar conditions.

2. This Journal, 1962, 39, 641.

3. Annalen, 1878, 183, 3.

TABLE III

 λ_{max} in alkaline ethanolic solutions.

Phenols.	Phthaleins.	3,4,5,6-Tetra-phenylphthaleins.	3,4,5,6-tetraphenyl- $\Delta^3,5$ -dihydrophthaleins.
Resorcinol	500 m μ	502 m μ	500 m μ
Orcinol	500	510	508
Tetrabromoresorcinol	525	540	538
Phenol	560	538	568
<i>o</i> -Cresol	570	544	550

TABLE IV

 λ_{max} in neutral ethanolic solutions.

Phenols.	3,4,5,6-Tetraphenylphthaleins.	3,4,5,6-tetraphenyl- $\Delta^3,5$ -dihydrophthaleins.
Resorcinol	495 m μ	480 and 490 m μ
Orcinol	435	
Tetrabromoresorcinol	550	538 m μ

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Erratum

On p. 380 of July issue, in Table I, column II, last line, read m.p. 170° against compound Xb.